

Nuclear Data Sampling Based Correlation Study Between a Full PWR Core at HZP and a Loaded Final Disposal Canister

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ABSTRACT

One of the main challenges for the application of burnup credit (BUC) in criticality safety evaluations (CSE) for the safe final disposal of used nuclear fuel (UNF), such as in deep geological repositories (DGRs), lies in the validation of the nuclide compositions and related nuclear data used in such analyses. The current basis for validation studies primarily consists in experiments with fresh fuel, whose nuclide compositions differ significantly from those of UNF. At PSI, nuclide vectors of irradiated fuel assemblies (FA) are determined via reference deterministic core-follow models (CASMO5/SIMULATE-3/5). Recently, these computed fuel compositions were successfully validated, in conjunction with the employed nuclear data library, against start-up in-core measurements for a full pressurized water reactor (PWR) core under hot zero power (HZP) conditions. This paper presents a correlation study between a final disposal canister loaded with spent nuclear FAs and the full PWR core at HZP, the burned nuclide compositions of which have been determined in the same way. The motivation for this work is the extension of the validation basis for BUC in CSE by configurations featuring burned fuel and eventually reduce over-conservatism in the calculation of upper subcritical limits (USLs) and associated nuclear criticality safety (NCS) criteria.

Keywords: Burnup credit, nuclear criticality safety, final disposal, spent nuclear fuel

1. INTRODUCTION

The validation basis for criticality calculations currently relies on critical benchmark experiments exclusively featuring fresh fuel. A comprehensive collection of such experiments is provided by the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) Handbook [1]. This limitation poses a major challenge, particularly for the validation of calculated nuclide compositions used in criticality safety evaluations (CSEs) employing burnup credit (BUC). The BUC approach accounts for the reduced reactivity of irradiated fuel due to the depletion of fissile isotopes and the buildup of neutron absorbers during reactor operation. Since the nuclide compositions of used nuclear fuel (UNF) differ substantially from those of fresh fuel, the correlation between application cases and the existing validation basis is significantly reduced and hence directly affecting the strictness and, in consequence, the ability to comply with underlying nuclear criticality safety (NCS) criteria.

At the Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI), reference deterministic core-follow models (CASMO5/SIMULATE-3/5¹) have been developed and validated for the Swiss nuclear power plants [2]. These models are the basis for a neutronic version of a “cycle check-up” (CHUP) methodology, also under development at PSI. The CHUP method transfers the evolved compositions and thermal-hydraulic/operational boundary conditions (including fuel and moderator temperatures, control rod position and boron critical concentration) into Monte Carlo (MC) neutron transport models [3]. This enables high-fidelity numerical solutions with established MC codes to problems that extend beyond the capabilities of

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¹ For different reactors different SIMULATE versions are used in the present reference models

deterministic nodal codes used for routine full-core simulations, such as determining intra-pin power distributions or local power gradients.

Recently, a full PWR core model, generated with the CHUP methodology, was validated against in-core measurements at hot zero power (HZIP) conditions [4-6]. Because the nuclide compositions in this full PWR core model was derived using the same computational approach as in earlier studies with the preliminary final disposal canister (ELB; Endlagerbehälter) design [7,8]—developed by the Swiss National Technical Competence Centre for deep geological disposal of radioactive waste (Nagra)—a direct nuclear data -related correlation study between the two model types became feasible. The motivation of the present work is to extend the validation basis for BUC in CSE by configurations featuring burned fuel, thereby reducing the over-conservatism in the determination of upper subcritical limits (USLs) for CSEs of UNF [8,9].

2. MONTE CARLO MODELS AND SIMULATIONS

2.1. Loaded Final Disposal Canister

The preliminary ELB design developed by Nagra and considered in this study, consists in a carbon steel cylinder almost 5 m long, with an outer diameter of 105 cm and ready to fit 4 PWR FAs in separate carbon steel boxes inserted and welded, see Figure 1 [10,11]. No strong neutron absorbers are included by design.

Figure 1. Left: Cross sectional sketch of the final disposal canister made of carbon steel. $R_{in} = 38.5$ cm, $R_{out} = 52.5$ cm, $A = 21.5$ cm (side of the FA top head), $B = 23.5$ cm (inner dimension of the FA box), $C = 25.5$ cm (box center-to-center distance) [10]. Right: 3-dimensional visualisation of the preliminary final disposal canister design [11].

The canister model considers a loading with 4 PWR-FAs having the same nuclear and mechanical design. A FA has a 15×15 array of fuel pins containing UO_2 enriched to 4.94 wt.% ^{235}U and 20 guide tubes. The correlation study was performed for the fresh FA as well as for the selected assembly averaged discharge burnups of 17.61, 33.82, 50.47, 61.92 and 72.75 GWd/tHM, corresponding to five operation cycles. Criticality calculations to obtain the k_{eff} of the ELB were performed for all these burnup values and for cooling times of 0 and 50,000 years. The presented canister model was already subject of a study quantifying nuclear data uncertainties. The data sets produced by this previous work have been used also for the present correlation study. For more details about the canister model development and made assumptions, the reader be referred to the journal article [7].

2.2. Full PWR Core

Performing core-follow simulations with Monte Carlo codes pose a great challenge due to the necessity of incorporating thermal-hydraulic feedback and generating evolved fuel composition for the cycle of interest by taking into account the entire irradiation history of the loaded FAs over previous cycles. The very high demand for computational power and memory hence inhibits the practical exploitation of Monte Carlo (MC) based neutron transport codes to provide high-fidelity numerical solutions to problems beyond the modelling capabilities of conventional core simulation methods. At PSI, a cycle check-up methodology (CHUP) is under development to overcome this burden. Recently, a full PWR core model for a hot zero power operating condition of a Swiss PWR using an updated CHUP methodology, automatizing the information extraction from reference core models, was successfully verified and validated, see Figure 2 [6]. The full-core MC model used in the present correlation study, includes UNF compositions generated by the SNF code [12] for each pin, based on validated deterministic core-follow and a clustering process described in [4].

Figure 2. Full PWR core modeled with Sepent2: radial plane (Left), axial plane (Right) [6].

2.3. Sampling Method and Monte Carlo Simulations

The criticality calculations for the loaded ELB were performed with the MCNP6® code (version 6.2; see <https://mcnp.lanl.gov> for details on the MCNP® software trademark), while Serpent (version V2.2.0 [13]) was applied for the full PWR core simulations. The Monte Carlo calculation uncertainties of the results for the loaded ELB were in average 24 pcm and 12 pcm for the full PWR core simulations. As nuclear data library, ENDF/B-VII.1 was used in all the simulations. To conduct the correlation study, 200 data sets of perturbed nuclear data in the form of ACE formatted files were generated with the Nuclear data Uncertainty Stochastic Sampling method (NUSS) [14], which applies perturbations in groups to pointwise nuclear data given in the specific ACE format based on the covariance data provided with ENDF/B-VII.1. The same nuclear data sets were already used for a ND uncertainty quantification in connection with CSE for UNF disposal with the ELB [7].

The criticality calculations for the loaded ELB and the full PWR core were then performed for each of these ND data sets and the Pearson correlation coefficients determined, see Figure 3. The highest correlation of 0.71 between loaded ELB and full PWR core was obtained for a burnup of 17.61 GWd/tHM and a cooling time of 50,000 years for the UNF assemblies. Due to the discrete set of only 6 data points per cooling time, it is not excluded that ELB and PWR core could correlate stronger around the burnup of 17.61 GWd/tHM, given the slope of the correlation trend, however, the maximal correlation is most likely not significantly higher than 0.71.

Figure 4 shows the scatter plot of the 200 calculated keff values calculated for the loaded ELB and the full PWR core at maximal correlation, i.e. at 17.61 GWd/tHM burnup and 50,000 years of cooling time. Despite the rather limited sample size of just 200, the correlation between the keff values appears as robust.

A comparison of the results with another correlation study between the loaded ELB and PSI's validation suite of in total 149 International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) experimental benchmarks puts the presented correlation into the relevant context, see Figure 5. The correlations between the loaded ELB and the ICSBEP low-enriched uranium criticality test (LCT) benchmark cases (cases 1-122) with fresh UO_2 fuel are all higher than 0.71. Only mixed-oxide criticality test (MCT) benchmark cases correlate similarly or lower than the configurations analyzed in the present study.

Figure 3. Correlation between loaded ELB and full PWR core model.

Figure 4. Pearson correlation between ELB and full PWR core visualized for an ELB loading with FAs of 17.61 GWd/tHM burnup and 50,000 years of cooling time.

Figure 5. Pearson correlation between loaded ELBs and the PSI validation suite of 149 selected ICSBEP benchmarks. Cases 1-122 correspond to LCT, cases 123-149 to MCT experimental benchmarks. The labels can0 – can61 denote ELB loadings with the respective FAs of 0 – 61.92 GWd/tHM burnup. The sample sizes to obtain the plotted correlations were 300 for each benchmark case and loaded ELB.

It is notable and expected that the correlation between the ELB canister loaded with UNF and the LCT cases decreases with fuel burnup, while it increases for the MCT cases, in line with the rising concentration of Pu isotopes and the decreasing concentration of ^{235}U in the UNF as a function of burnup.

3. CONCLUSIONS

This study represents a first attempt to expand the existing validation basis for nuclide compositions calculated for use in CSE employing BUC. The results reveal a moderate correlation of maximally 0.71 between the analyzed configurations of an ELB loaded with FAs of varying burnup and cooling time and the full PWR core. This level of correlation does not exceed that observed between all ICSBEP LCT benchmark experiments in the PSI validation suite with fresh fuel and the loaded ELB, even in the case where the ELB contains FAs with a high burnup of 61.92 GWd/tHM.

Consequently, the investigated full PWR core configuration appears to lack perfect representativity in terms of layout, geometry, material composition, and/or fuel nuclide inventory to serve as a all-sufficient basis for validating the calculated nuclide compositions applied in CSE for the final disposal of UNF using the ELB.

Nevertheless, the value of the PWR HZP models representing start-up tests should not be underestimated based on the observed correlation study results. One must keep in mind that the ICSBEP benchmarks, primarily used for validation of criticality calculations worldwide, lack the presence of minor actinides and fission products. Thus, there is a substantial validation gap which has to be addressed in order to support practical BUC applications. This is why the full core start-up models with actual irradiated PWR fuel have outmost value.

It is true that the moderate values of the correlation coefficient indicate that the PWR model is not perfectly representative for the ELB models with UNF, as concerns the spectral characteristics and nuclear data effects. A reduced spacing between the FAs, corresponding to thinner steel basket elements, as inside the PWR core could increase the correlation. However, such a modification of the ELB design would lead to higher keff values, which is clearly undesirable from a criticality safety standpoint.

Nevertheless, the PWR start-up HZP models cover that part of the validation needs, which is difficult to compensate otherwise (though very valuable “Haut Taux de Combustion (HTC)” critical experiments were conducted in France in the 1980s with the fuel containing ^{241}Am [15], at first this experimental data is proprietary and at second it still does not cover the validation gap for all relevant minor actinides and on top of that, fission products). In overall, the question of adequate experimental coverage is a big research subject in itself and can go far beyond a direct assessment solely based on the values of the Person correlation coefficients. Such discussion, however, goes beyond the scope of the

present paper and the focus of this work was just to provide the first estimations on the representativity metrics, using the Person coefficient as such.

Finally, it should be noted that the correlation between the full PWR core and ELB configurations containing MOX FAs may be higher than that observed for loadings with burned UO₂ fuel. Therefore, extending this correlation study to include MOX fuel assembly designs could be valuable.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development/Nuclear Energy Agency. *International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) Handbook*. OECD/NEA, Paris, France (2022/2023). URL https://www.oecd-nea.org/jcms/pl_20291/international-criticality-safety-benchmark-evaluation-project-icsbep-handbook
- [2] H. Ferroukhi, K. Hofer, J-M. Hollard, A. Vasiliev, M.A. Zimmermann. “Core Modelling and Analysis of the Swiss Nuclear Power Plants for Qualified R&D Applications.” In *Proceedings of the PHYSOR-2008*. American Nuclear Society, Interlaken, Switzerland (2008)
- [3] M. Pecchia, H. Ferroukhi, A. Vasiliev, P. Grimm. “Studies of intra-pin power distributions in operated BWR fuel assemblies using MCNP with a cycle check-up methodology.” *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, **129**, pp. 67–78 (2019). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2019.01.047>
- [4] L. Berry, A. Vasiliev, M. Hursin, D. Rochman, M. Frankl, H. Ferroukhi. “Towards establishment of an efficient approach for validation of PWR full core Monte Carlo simulations at hot zero power conditions.” *Prog. Nucl. Energy*, **172**, 105203 (2024). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2024.105203>.
- [5] L. Berry, A. Vasiliev, D. Rochman, M. Hursin, M. Frankl, H. Ferroukhi. “Upgrading the neutronic version of the PSI cycle check-up methodology for full core PWR Monte Carlo simulations.” *Joint International Conference on Supercomputing in Nuclear Applications + Monte Carlo (SNA + MC) 2024*, Paris, France, October 20-24, 2024. URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202430213004>.
- [6] L. Berry, A. Vasiliev, D. Rochman, M. Hursin, M. Frankl, H. Ferroukhi. “Application of the PSI cycle check-up methodology for full-core Monte Carlo simulations verified using pin power estimates and validated for hot zero power conditions.” *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, **211**, 110939 (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2024.110939>.
- [7] M. Frankl, M. Hursin, D. Rochman, A. Vasiliev, H. Ferroukhi. “Nuclear data uncertainty quantification in criticality safety evaluations for spent nuclear fuel geological disposal.” *Appl. Sci.*, **11** (14), 6499 (2021). URL <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11146499>.
- [8] M. Frankl, A. Vasiliev, D. Rochman, H. Ferroukhi, M. Wittel, S. Pudollek. “Refinement of the Loading Curve Determination Methodology and Modeling for Swiss PWR Spent Fuel Final Disposal Canisters.” *ICNC 2023 - The 12th International Conference on Nuclear Criticality Safety*. Sendai, Japan, October 1-6, 2023.
- [9] A. Vasiliev, M. Frankl, D. Rochman, H. Ferroukhi. “Case Study on the Performance of Bayesian and Frequentist Statistical Approaches for Criticality Safety Evaluations with Used Nuclear Fuel.” *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, pp. 1–17 (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295639.2025.2525033>.
- [10] R. Patel, C. Punshon, J. Nicholas, P. Bastid, R. Zhou, C. Schneider, N. Bagshaw, D. Howse, E. Hutchinson, R. Asano et al. *Canister Design Concepts for Disposal of Spent Fuel and High-Level Waste*. Nagra Technical Report 12-06, Nationale Genossenschaft für die Lagerung Radioaktiver Abfälle, Wettingen, Switzerland (2012).

- [11] L.H. Johnson, M. Niemeyer, G. Klubertanz et al. *Calculations of the temperature evolution of a repository for spent fuel, vitrified high-level waste and intermediate level waste in opalinus clay*. NTB-01-04, Nationale Genossenschaft für die Lagerung Radioaktiver Abfälle, Wetingen, Switzerland (2002).
- [12] Simeonov, T., & Wemple, C. *Advances in Studsvik's system for spent fuel analyses*. EPJ Web Conf., 247, 02021, EDP Sciences (2021). URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202124702021>
- [13] Leppänen, J., Valtavirta, V., Rintala, A., & Tuominen, R. *Status of Serpent Monte Carlo code in 2024*. EPJ Nuclear Sci. Technol., 11, 3, EDP Sciences (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjn/2024031>
- [14] T. Zhu, A. Vasiliev, H. Ferroukhi, A. Pautz. "ACE-formatted nuclear data using stochastic sampling method." *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, **75**, pp. 713–722 (2015). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2014.09.013>.
- [15] D.E. Mueller, K.R. Elam, P.B. Fox. *Evaluation of the French Haut Taux de Combustion (HTC) Critical Experiment Data*. NUREG/CR-6979 (ORNL/TM-2007/083), prepared for the US Nuclear Regulatory Commission by Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Oak Ridge, USA (2008).